

PROFICIENCY IN ALL 4 SKILLS IN ENGLISH

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ABSTRACT

English is a world language, providing access to diverse societies and expanding people's horizons both personally and professionally. The ability to communicate in English builds connections and mutual understanding between people across the world. Each of the 4 skills of listening, speaking, reading and writing has an important role to play.

***Key words:** assessment, mandated, **KWL Technique**. Predictions, Getting the primary, **Sunshine outline**.*

Introduction

We aim to improve the quality of English education and to support the Japanese government's English Education Reform agenda, drawing on the experience and expertise of the UK, where both the language itself and learning approaches have evolved over hundreds of years.

We have been teaching thousands of young learners and adults for many years in Japan, as well as supporting teachers in the state education system. In that time, we have always sought to develop students' practical English language skills and their confidence to use them. To strengthen the English language education system, we believe it is essential to address learning, teaching and assessment in an integrated way. We understand that this is also the ambition behind Japan's new Courses of Study.

Learning: Students need the ability to use English effectively in practical situations; to understand new information, ideas, or enjoy foreign culture through listening and reading and to communicate what they want, share how they feel, or discuss opinions and ideas through speaking or writing. Knowledge of vocabulary and grammar should play an active role in building the ability and the confidence to communicate.

Teaching in schools: The education reform drives change in the way that English is taught. We support teachers nationwide to ensure that they can provide effective and motivating lessons for their students. We work to support teachers' professional development; working to assess their needs and helping to improve the quality of teaching in the classroom. Our professional development covers techniques for teaching all four skills, but our recent work has often focused on helping teachers with practical ideas for teaching interactive speaking, as mandated in the new Course of Study.

The four skills of language learning are Listening, Speaking, Reading, and Writing. They are four capabilities that allow an individual to comprehend, produce, and use the language in effective interpersonal communication. Having a good English level means understanding and producing the language, so we should teach and develop all the four language skills in our students.

Listening difficulties:

The speed

It is related to how many people are there in the conversation and how quickly they speak.

Vocabulary:

It is related to the inability of students to understand the listening text if they cannot understand the vocabulary included.

Structures:

It is related to the inability of students to understand the listening text if they cannot understand the key structures included.

The length and the topic:**Intonation:**

The intonation and stress of English native speakers are different from speakers of other languages.

Stages of teaching a listening activity***Before listening:***

Prepare students for the listening activity by:

- Making them interested with an interesting introduction to the topic.
- Giving them a reason for listening and asking them a question to answer.
- Explaining the new words.
- Explaining the new structures.

During listening:

- Students listen to the text for the first time.
- Helping them guess what will happen next after listening to a part of the text.
- They compare their predictions after their first listening.
- Ask some questions to answer before they listen a second time.
- Students listen a second time.
- They do some activities e.g. filling in a table while listening the second time.

Post listening

- Check students' understanding of the whole listening text by asking more questions on details.
- The teacher reads aloud the text (the story) from the audio script with five or six mistakes (not the grammar of course). Students correct these mistakes either immediately or by making a list of these mistakes and tell the teacher of them after listening.

Teaching Reading

Reading is the second receptive language skill which includes the following three levels in sequence.

1. Getting the primary, directed meaning of a word, idea or sentence.
2. Getting what the writer is trying to say to us “between the lines” without actually stating it.
3. Analyzing what the writer says or means.
4. **Techniques to teach reading:**

1. KWL Technique (What I know – What I want to know – What I learned)

Teaching Writing

There are three stages to deal with writing: before writing, during writing, and after writing.

Before writing (3 steps):

Students get enough ideas and information necessary for writing. It helps learners focus on the purpose and possible readers of their written work before starting writing.

1. *Grouping discussion.*

Encourage your students to discuss a certain topic in groups. The advantages of this are:

- It helps students get different viewpoints.
- Stronger students can help weaker students.
- It helps the teacher find out whether his students have enough vocabulary and are good at language structures.

2. *Sunshine outline.*

- Students draw rays coming from the sun and write a question word on each ray: who, what...etc.
- Help students think of possible questions that begin with these question words. Then, they write a phrase or two to answer these questions.

3. Oral brainstorming.

This is done orally. It involves the use of questions. The teacher can write these questions on the board and ask each student to think out answers to them. The teacher should bear in mind the following points:

- Accept all students' answers.
- There are no wrong or right answers.
- Never force the students to follow your viewpoints.
- Never interrupt the students during answering.

The teacher discusses the answers with his students. Then, he asks them to go to the next step.

4. Interviewing.

Students interview each other. They share viewpoints and ideas. They usually share their personal experiences and think about them during the interview. This makes students relaxed and reduces the fear of writing.

Conclusion:

It may help the individuals to develop the desire to read and write in order to learn willingly and comfortably. In conclusion, the four language skills of listening, speaking, reading and writing are important in order to improve everyday life communicative interactions.

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